

EFFECT OF WIDE BASE TIRE ON RIGID PAVEMENT PERFORMANCE IN EGYPT

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ABSTRACT:

The fatigue life of the rigid pavement is affected by different factors, the most important of these factors are axle loading, the spacing between axles in one axle group, and also the type of used tires. The main objective of this study is to evaluate the performance of rigid pavement due to various tire type (wide-base and conventional tire) by calculating the number of cycles to fatigue failure for rigid pavement and the Axle Factor (AF), to make a comparison between the different values of the Axle Factor for each tire type. This comparison showed the effect of different tire on fatigue damage life and identifying the performance of the rigid pavement. The finite element software program DYNA-SLAB was used to calculate the stresses under the various axle. The fatigue life was assessed by the Mechanistic-Empirical Pavement Design Guide (M-EPDG) equation depending on the result of stresses from the DYNA-SLAB program then calculated the Axle Factor for each axle type. The results indicated that a wide-base tire is the worst performance of rigid pavement compared with a conventional tire because the Axle Factor is increased by about 51%, 33%, and 34% for single, tandem, and tridem axle respectively. Also, fatigue life was decreased by an average of 34% of the conventional tire. Therefore, The legal loads in the Egyptian Code for single, tandem and tridem using a wide-base tire should be decreased by 51%, 33%, and 34% respectively from those that use conventional tires.

Keywords

“Wide base Tire”, “ rigid pavement” ,“ Fatigue”, “ Load Factor”

1. Introduction

Two cases of rigid pavement will be analyzed to investigate the pavement life for different axle configurations, including the influence of different axle spacing and the influence of tire type. To evaluate, compare and determine the pavement response the pavement life for two cases due to different axle

configuration and tire type, the following analysis will proceed.

K. Chatti and H. Salama (2008) [1] displayed that by using load pluses that were equivalent to the passage of an entire axle group was found that the fatigue life of a plain concrete mixture under various truck axle configurations was directly defined from a repeated four-point beam test in addition to evaluate The S-N curves for each axle configuration. The laboratory investigated refer to that by increasing number of axles the fatigue damage was increased due to various axle configuration within an axle group for a given stress ratio but the damage per axle was less than the single axle for the multiple axles in same stress ratio. Based on this results it must to rise the axle factors for multiple axles as the stress ratio decreases.

Yuehong Su and others [2] established the physical road structure sample of vehicle SF31904 moving on the cement concrete pavement. The finite element software ABAQUS program was used to analyze and calculate the tensile stress in various cases. Figure (2-5) shows relative curve for maximal tensile stress and slab. The results displayed that reduced in maximum stress happened in case of use the basic structure and earthen foundation module is exceed 30 MPa under SF31904 heavy mineral, but by increased the thickness to 50 cm there was no apparent decrease in tensile stress. The fatigue was neglected because the rigid pavement of opencast coal mine only was used when the vehicle was maintained in the factory and the axle load function number of times are very few.

Swati Roy Maitra and others (2013) [3] presented a method for calculating the stress in concrete pavement resulting from composite of tire load and positive temperature gradient using finite element model. A comparison with IRC: 58 (2002) displayed that the stress, specially temperature stress was overestimated by use IRC method. Therefore, it was suggested a modification Bradbury's temperature stress coefficient which can used to evaluation the curling stress on concrete pavement.

Rezwana Kabir (2015) [4] compared between the results of stress, strain, and deflections under the loading of multi-axles (11 axles) of heavy Michigan trucks and a standard 5-axle semi-trailer including the impacts of various tire configurations. The finite element computer software program (ISLAB2000) has been used. Results display that

has a higher fatigue damage potential for the standard truck during daytime under positive temperature gradient across slab while the Michigan trucks provide a greater fatigue damage potential during nighttime under negative temperature gradient.

Mohamed Zakaria and others (2017) [5] displayed an estimate the new fatigue models of Mechanistic-Empirical Pavement Design Guide for both type of pavement flexible and rigid for multiple axle loads and to determine the validity of using this method of design in the Arab Republic of Egypt. The comparison between the results of Mechanistic-Empirical Pavement Design Guide and of Michigan Department of Transportation's laboratory tests which indicate that the average overall error was + 20%. The stress value is relatively high. However, it is still possible to use the M-EPDG to predict the fatigue life of rigid pavement in Egypt.

2. Background about fatigue damage of rigid pavement

The fatigue damage is the most dangerous and most frequent collapse of the concrete pavement, which attracted researchers to more attention and more studies to evaluate the age of fatigue failure in the rigid pavement. There are a lot of methods were used to calculate the fatigue life of rigid pavement such as the medium stress method, the dispersive energy method, and the maximum stress method.

2.1 Previous Concrete Fatigue Models

Table [1] shows the most fatigue model as they listed in the Michigan Department of Transportation's, MDOT's study (Chatti *et al*, 2009) and other different research.

Table [1]: List of the previous fatigue model.

$\text{Log } N = 2.13 \left(\frac{\text{MR}}{\sigma} \right)^{1.2}$	Darter (1990)
$\text{Log } N = 11.81 - 12.1765 \left(\frac{\sigma}{\text{MR}} \right)$ for $0.5 \leq \left(\frac{\sigma}{\text{MR}} \right) \leq 1$	Portland Cement Association (1963)
$\text{Log } N = 17.61 - 17.61 \left(\frac{\sigma}{\text{MR}} \right)$	Zero-Maintenance (1977)
$\text{Log } N = -1.736 \left(\frac{\sigma}{\text{MR}} \right) + 4.284$ for $\frac{\sigma}{\text{MR}} \geq 1.25$ $\text{Log } N = 2.8127 \left(\frac{\sigma}{\text{MR}} \right)^{-1.2214}$ for $\frac{\sigma}{\text{MR}} \leq 1.25$	NCHRP (1992)
$\text{Log } N = 1.323 \left(\frac{\text{MR}}{\sigma} \right) + 0.588$	Foxworthy (1985)
$N_f = \left[\frac{1.2968}{\sigma/\text{MR}} \right]^{32.57}$	Roesler (1998)

$N_f = \left[\frac{2.689}{\sigma/\text{MR}} \right]^{21.79}$	Roesler (2004)
$\text{Log } N = \frac{1 - (0.465 \text{ SR} + 0.088 \log T)}{0.153 (1 - 0.297 R)}$	Rao (2005)
$N = \left[\frac{4.2577}{\text{SR} - 0.4325} \right]^{3.268}$ When $0.45 \leq \text{SR} \leq 0.55$ $\text{Log } N = \frac{0.9718 - \text{SR}}{0.0828}$ for $\text{SR} > 0.55$	Portland Cement Association (1980)
$\frac{\sigma_{\text{max}}}{\text{MOR}} = 1 - \beta(1 - R) \log_{10} N$	Tepfers and Kutti 1979
$\text{Log } N = \left[\frac{-\text{SR}^{-10.24} \log(1 - p)}{0.0112} \right]^{-0.217}$	American Concrete Pavement Association

2.2 M-EPDG Fatigue Model

The Mechanistic-Empirical Design Guide (M-EPDG) method can be used to estimate the fatigue life of the rigid pavement. The M-EPDG uses the following calibrated equation [1] to determine the fatigue life of concrete pavement (ARA, 2004).

$$\text{Log } (N_{i,j,k,l,m,n}) = C_1 * \left(\frac{\text{MR}_i}{\sigma_{i,l,k,m,n}} \right)^{C_2} + 0.4371 \quad [1]$$

Where:

- $N_{i,j,k,l,m,n}$ = Allowable number of load application at condition i,j,k,l,m,n
- i = Age (accounts for PCC rupture modulus adjustment, layer bond quality, shoulder deterioration LTE)
- j = Month (accounts for base shift and effective subgrade reaction dynamic modulus).
- k = Axle configuration (single, tandem, and bottom-up cracking tridem; short, medium, and long top-down cracker)
- l = load level (incremental load for each axle type)
- m = temperature difference
- n = traffic path
- MR_i = Modulus of rupture of PCC at age "i" (Psi)
- C_1 & C_2 = Calibration constant (2.0, 1.22).
- $\sigma_{i,j,k,l,m,n}$ = The applied stress at condition (i, j, k, l, m, n).

3. Research Methodology

To evaluate the performance of concrete pavement under a different type of tires, the following steps were proceeded:

- The horizontal tensile stresses were calculated due to different axles [single, tandem, and tridem] for both conventional and wide base tire
- The fatigue life was calculated using the M-E PDG procedure for concrete pavement.
- Axle loads for various groups of axles were computed.
- Make a comparison between the calculated axle factors for conventional and wide-base tires.

Figure [1] demonstrates descriptions of the research methodology used to assess concrete pavement efficiency.

Figure [1]: Flow chart of the research methodology.

4. Data Collection

Different types of truck configurations were chosen to determine the difference in tire types, the spacing between axles in one axle group, and the most common tire size used in trucks in Egypt. These different cases were selected to evaluate the performance of concrete pavement under various axle configurations. The axle loads were taken according to the Egyptian Code of road. It was found that the most common spacing between axles in one axle group in Egypt is 1.36m (54in). Table [2] displays the details of different cases with different axle types.

Table [2]: Details of different tire type

Group	Axle type	Axle load (ton)	Tire type	Tire load (ton)
A	Single axle	13	Conventional	3.25
			Wide base	6.50
B	Tandem Axle	20	Conventional	2.50
			Wide base	5.00
C	Tridem axle	30	Conventional	2.50
			Wide base	5.00

5. Calculation of Contact Area

Due to the variety of tires size and loads, the contact areas will change accordingly. So, the calculation of the contact area was based on the most commonly used tire sizes, as follows:

- For conventional tire, the size is 295/80R22.5.
- And size 455/50R22.5 for a wide-base tire.

The contact area is calculated by using the following equation:

$$A_c = \pi (0.3L)^2 + (0.4L)(0.6L) = 0.5227L^2$$

$$\text{or } L = (A_c / 0.5227)^{0.5} \quad [2]$$

Where:

A_c = equivalent contact area.

L = Length of contact area

Table [3] and [4] show the calculated contact area of wide-base and conventional tires according to different loads.

Table [3]: Contact area of wide-base tires

Loading (lb)	Tire Pressure (Psi)	Contact area (in ²)	Length (inch)	Width (inch)
11024 [5 ton]	120	91.9	11.6	8
14330 [6.5 ton]	120	119.5	13.3	9.2
Average			12.5	8.6

Table [4]: Contact area of conventional tires

Loading (lb)	Tire Pressure (Psi)	Contact area (in ²)	Length (inch)	Width (inch)
5512 [2.5 ton]	120	46	8.2	5.7
7165 [3.25 ton]	120	60	9.5	6.5
Average			9.0	6.1

6. Curling Stress

The curling stress due to the change in temperature between the upper and lower of the slab was added to the calculated stress from the DYNA-SLAB program. Equation [3] shows the edge curling stress due to 1° C change between the top and bottom of the slab.

$$\sigma_t = \frac{C_x * E * e * (\Delta t)}{2} \quad [3]$$

To calculate the coefficient in direction of calculated stress, the radius of relative stiffness should be calculated by using the following equation [4]:

$$l = \sqrt[4]{\frac{E * h^3}{12(1 - \mu^2)k}} \quad [4]$$

Where:

- σ = Slab (Edge or Interior or Corner) warping stress
- E = Modulus of elasticity of PCC (4.0E+06) psi
- e = Thermal Coefficient of PCC ($5 \times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{F}$)
- Δt = temperature differential between the top and bottom of the slab ($1^{\circ}\text{C} = 33.8^{\circ}\text{F}$)
- C_x = coefficient in direction of calculated stress
- r = Radius of relative stiffness
- h = Slab thickness (10-inch)
- K = Modulus of subgrade reaction (150 psi)
- μ = Poisson's ratio for PCC (0.15)

$$l = \sqrt[4]{\frac{E \cdot h^3}{12(1-\mu^2)k}} = \sqrt[4]{\frac{4.0 \times 10^6 \cdot 10^3}{12(1-0.15^2)150}} = 38.8 \text{ inch}$$

$$\frac{L}{l} = \frac{15 \times 12}{38.8} = 4.6$$

From figure [2] get $C_x = 0.57$

$$\sigma_x = \frac{0.57 \cdot 4.0 \times 10^6 \cdot 5 \times 10^{-6} \cdot 33.8}{2} = 193 \text{ psi}$$

Figure [2] warping stress coefficient

7. Estimate the Number of Cycle to Fatigue Failure Using M-EPDG

To estimate the number of cycles to fatigue failure, the DYNA-SLAB finite element program was used to calculate the tensile stress under different axle configurations (single, tandem, and tridem). The assumptions which were taken in the program and a constant in all cases are:

- Modulus of elasticity = 4.0 E+06 Psi.
- Poisson ratio = 0.15.
- Slab thickness = 10 inch.
- Dual spacing = 16.4 inch
- Modulus of subgrade reaction = 150 Psi.
- Load transfer in the x-direction by the dowel bars only.
- Dowel and concrete interaction = 1.52E+06.
- The average contact area of a conventional tire = 9.0-length and 6.1-width
- The average contact area of a wide base tire = 12.5-length and 8.6-width
- Dimension of slabs = 12 ft wide * 15 ft long.

7.1 Influence of different tire type on the fatigue life of the rigid pavement.

There are two types of tires, conventional and wide base tire. This study will evaluate the effect of change tire type on the Egyptian Rigid Pavement Roads by calculating the Axle Factor of fatigue failure according to a different type of tire from the following axle configuration cases. The spacing between axles in one axle group is 1.36m (54-inch). Figure [3] illustrates the tensile stress for single, tandem and tridem axles with different tire types which were calculated by using the DYNA-SLAB program.

Conventional tire

Wide base tire

a) Single axle dual tire tensile stress with 13 ton axle load

Conventional tire

b) Tandem axle tensile stress with 20 ton axle load

c) Tridem axle tensile stress with 30 ton axle load

Figure [3] DYNA-SLAB tensile stress results for different types of tires

Table [5] displays the total tensile stress. Additionally, table [6] shows the number of cycles to fatigue failure $[N_F]$ for each axle which was calculated by using the M-EPDG equation. The Axle Factors for each axle group were calculated based on the equation [5].

$$AF = \frac{\text{Damage of the axle group}}{\text{Damage of single axle}} = \frac{1}{\frac{N_f \text{ of axle group}}{N_f \text{ of single axle}}} = \frac{N_f \text{ standard axle (18 Kip)}}{N_f \text{ of axles}} \quad [5]$$

Table [7] shows the Axle Factors for each axle group depend on the standard axle 18kips.

Table [5]: Total longitudinal stress plus curling stress

Axle group	Tire Type	Stress (Psi)		
		Axle [1]	Axle [2]	Axle [3]
Standard axle (18 Kip)	Conventional	316		
Single axle (13 ton) (28 Kip)	Conventional	389		
	Wide base	405		
Tandem axle (20 ton) (44 Kip)	Conventional	322	332	
	Wide base	333	343	
Tridem axle (30 ton) (66 Kip)	Conventional	300	309	313
	Wide base	309	319	322

Table [6]: Number of cycle load to fatigue failure

Axle group	Tire Type	N_F		
		Axle [1]	Axle [2]	Axle [3]
Standard axle (18 Kip)	Conventional	181310		
Single axle (13 ton) (28 Kip)	Conventional	15087		
	Wide base	9978		
Tandem axle (20 ton) (44 Kip)	Conventional	140943	94727	
	Wide base	91169	63023	
Tridem axle (30 ton) (66 Kip)	Conventional	374924	246604	206470
	Wide base	246604	159647	140943

Table [7]: Axle Factor using M-EPDG equation.

Axle group	Tire Type	AF			
		Axle [1]	Axle [2]	Axle [3]	Total AF
Standard axle (18 Kip)	Conventional	1.00			1.00
Single axle (13 ton) (28 Kip)	Conventional	12.02			12.02
	Wide base	18.17			18.17
Tandem axle (20 ton) (44 Kip)	Conventional	1.29	1.91		3.20
	Wide base	1.99	2.88		4.87
Tridem axle (30 ton) (66 Kip)	Conventional	0.48	0.74	0.88	2.10
	Wide base	0.74	1.14	1.29	3.17

7.1.1 Comparing between the Axle Factors of different tire types.

Figure [4] displays the comparison between the Axle Factors for different axle configurations. The comparison demonstrates that the Axle Factor of the wide-base tire is higher than the Axle Factor of conventional tire by 51%,

52%, and 51% for single, tandem and tridem axle respectively, and decreased the fatigue life with an average of 34% from the conventional tire. Therefore, The legal loads in the Egyptian Code for single, tandem and tridem wide-base tires should be decreased by 51%, 52%, and 51% for single, tandem and tridem axle respectively. and, On the other hand, the traffic fees for trucks with wide-base tires should be higher than the fees for those using conventional tires. The following equation calculate the percentage of increasing in Axle Factor:

$$\% \text{ Increase in AF} = \frac{\text{AF of wide base} - \text{AF of conventional}}{\text{AF of conventional}} * 100$$

Table [8]: The percentage of increasing in Axle Factor's

Axle group	AF of conventional tire	AF of wide base tire	Increase in AF	% Increase in AF
Standard axle (18 Kip)	1.00			
Single axle (13 ton) (28 Kip)	12.02	18.17	6.15	51%
Tandem axle (20 ton) (44 Kip)	3.20	4.87	1.67	52%
Tridem axle (30 ton) (66 Kip)	2.10	3.17	1.07	51%

Figure [4]: Comparison between Axle Factor due to different tire type.

8. Conclusion

Based on the analysis, the main conclusion of this research can be summarized as follows:

- The Axle Factor of a wide-base tire higher than the Axle Factor of conventional tires.
- A wide base tire is increased the Axle Factor by 51%, 52% and 51% for single, tandem and tridem axle respectively.
- The legal loads in the Egyptian Code for single, tandem and tridem using a wide-base tire should be decreased by 51%, 52% and 51% respectively from those that use conventional tires.

9. Reference

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